

Development of Social Dominance Orientation Towards Caste Category Scale and Hindi Translation of Social Dominance Orientation Scale for Different Social Categories in India

Shraddhesh Kumar Tiwari^{1*}, Dhananjay Kumar², Anubhuti Dubey³

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop social dominance orientation towards caste/category scale in Hindi language and Hindi translation of four item social dominance scales. Both scales administered on 360 subjects (120 general category, 120 other backward category and 120 scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category). Exploratory factor analysis computed using “principle component extraction” method, with varimax rotation. Items loaded on two factors namely Dominance Enhancement and Dominance Attenuation. First factor explained 23.54% variance whereas; second factor explained 22.82% of variance. Total 45.85% variance of social dominance orientation towards caste category scale, were explained by both of these factors. Hindi translation of four item social dominance orientation scale (short version), yielded two factors: Hierarchy Enhancement and Hierarchy attenuation. First factor explained 34.19% variance and 30.21% variance was explained by second factor. Total 64.41% variance explained by these two factors. Alpha calculated to estimate psychometric properties. Both scales found to have good psychometric properties.

Keywords: *Social Dominance Orientation, Dominance Enhancement, Dominance Attenuation, Hierarchy Enhancement, Hierarchy Attenuation*

Social dominance orientation was first introduced as a component of Social Dominance Theory, which sought to explain the observation that social groups are organized into hierarchies in every studied human culture (Pratto et al 1994). A group-based hierarchy describes a social system that consists of at least one dominant group and one subordinate group. Group based hierarchy have been observed in every human society (Pratto, Sidanius, Stallworth, & Malle, 1994). Group-based hierarchy is, that it suggests how to treat with an individual within a society. Dryburgh (2014) argued that due to difference in group status within a hierarchy, individual in subordinate groups may have less access to resource and opportunities, and may even face limited access or no access to certain rights.

¹Post-Doctoral Fellow, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur, India

²Professor, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur, India

³Professor, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur, India

*Corresponding Author

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When we talk about Indian social structure and historical evidence, caste system is one of the main dimensions where people socially differentiated through class, religion, region, tribes, gender and language. Although this form of differentiation exists in all human societies, it become a problem when one or more dimensions overlap each other and become the sole basis of systematic ranking and unequal access to valued resource like wealth, income, power and prestige (Sekhon 2000). Hutton (1963) states that caste name is generally associated with occupation and, as mentioned before is a closed stratification, which make it endogamous. Indian caste system is a classification of people into four hierarchically ranked castes called varnas. These are classified to determine access to wealth, power and privilege. Leadership positions in society are monopolized by a few dominant castes (Pintane 2010). Division of people into Indian groups was based on aptitude, abilities and vocation. These divisions are known as caste and varnas namely Brahman, Kshatriy, Vaishy and Shudra. Two upper castes are ritually considered as superior to lower castes (Smith 1994). Rituals, customs, collective community ownership and status quo and simple division of labour characterized traditional societies. Historical division and categorization of society have taken form of social stratification. Over the past decades and centuries, these ideas about social stratification of upper caste and lower caste made people superior to inferior in groups and social interaction. Fiske and Neubers (1990), points out that salience of group membership does affect self-perception, impression of others, attitude and behaviour. Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher and Wetherell (1987) theorize that definition of self and others being a group member determines the way people engage in stereotyping, intergroup behaviour and otherwise acts. Tajfel and Turner (1986), states that group membership is an important constituent of self-concept. People tend to evaluate their in-group more favourably than another group. Social identity theory framed the social psychological understanding of how and when groups that are low in social standing will accept alleged inferiority and they will attempt to challenge (Ellemers, Wilke and Van Knippenberg 1993).

Social dominance orientation theory “postulates that societies minimize group conflict by creating consensus on ideologies that promote the superiority of one group over others”. Social Dominance Orientation is an individual difference variable that measures the degree to which a person prefers group-based hierarchies in society. If an individual is high in social dominance orientation, this suggests that they prefer inequality between social groups, whereas an individual low in social dominance orientation should prefer groups to be equal. The researchers proposed a systematic process by which these hierarchies might be created and maintained. They specified a number of factors and influences that are hypothesized to cause discrimination and prejudice at three levels: the level of the individual, the level of the group, and the level of society (Pratto, Sidanius, & Levin, 2006). Cultures and the individuals in them prescribe to widely accepted and shared ideologies that serve to either enhance or attenuate hierarchies (Pratto et al., 2006).

Hierarchy-enhancing ideologies prescribe behaviours that maintain group inequality, whereas hierarchy-attenuating ideologies prescribe behaviours that reduce inequality (Pratto, Tatar, & Conway-Lanz, 1999). Examples of hierarchy-enhancing ideologies include notions of fate, beliefs in a just world, or internal attributions of poverty, all of which serve to justify inequality. Examples of hierarchy-attenuating ideologies include social democracy, egalitarianism, and human rights, all which serve to mitigate the dominance of certain groups, while reducing the subordination of others. As these ideologies are proposed to exist at the system-wide level, they are theorized to influence the actions of social institutions.

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Institutions are assumed to have a significant influence on the positioning of groups, as institutions have access to a vast number of social resources and control their allocation resources.

A great deal of researches in western countries has been shown that social dominance orientation was positively correlated with measures of sexism, racism, nationalism, conservatism, cultural elitism, support for the military and attitudes towards wars of dominance (Pratto et al., 1994; Sidanius, Pratto, & Mitchell, 1994). Whereas, negatively correlated with measures of support for gay rights and women's rights, social welfare programs, environmental policy, altruism, noblesse oblige, and ameliorative racial policy (Pratto et al., 1994). The majority of social dominance orientation scales found to be correlated directly to the enhancement or reduction of inequality between groups. In addition, the broad range of groups represented in these variables demonstrates that social dominance orientation is a general attitudinal dimension towards social groups of differing group status, as opposed to a specific attitude towards particular groups.

According to group position model theory, the more powerful groups tend to move to and maintain a dominant power position over less powerful group. In essence, these powerful groups support social attitudes and beliefs and policies that place themselves to a greater advantage over lesser groups (Costello, & Hodson, 2011; Hodson, & Costello, 2007; Lindén, Björklund, & Bäckström, 2016; Sidanius & Pratto, 1999). In terms of race and ethnic relations American Whites tend to view race as a group position. They do not support policies that reallocate power and advantage to less powerful groups (Cokely et al., 2010; Crowson & Brandes, 2017; Duckitt & Sibley, 2007; Ho, Sidanius, Kteily, Sheehy-Skeffington, Pratto, Henkel, Foels, & Stewart, 2015; Oxendine, 2016b; Pratto et al.; Sidanius & Pratto; Sibley & Duckitt, 2008; Sibley, Robertson, & Wilson, 2006; Umphress, Simmons, Boswell, & Triana, 2008).

The role of social dominance orientation is considered a powerful construct in predicting intergroup behaviours and attitudes. Although SDO works as a unitary construct in social situations, it consists of two dimensions: SDO-D and SDO-E. The preference to dominate others for some groups is called SDO-Dominance, while a preference for intergroup relations having non-egalitarian behaviour is called SDO-Egalitarianism (Ho et al., 2012). Both dimensions are theoretically proven through criterion validity and confirmatory factor, so they are best predictors of intergroup outcomes (Ho et al., 2015). The mediating role of SDO between political conservatism, the denial of gender related anthropogenic climatic change, and male related conservatism was more comprehensively admired (Jylha, Cantal, Akrami, & Milfont, 2016). The hierarchy regulating strategies are reflected in having immigrant out-group offenders and differential judgments of national related in-group (Green, Thomsen, Sidanius, Staerkle, & Potanina, 2009). The role of Popularity among peer groups of adolescents can be predicted by social dominance orientation. Men as compared to women express higher levels of social dominance orientation. In this way, social dominance orientation is considered as a variable of individual differences that reflect support for unequal, hierarchical environment among groups. The gender differences in social dominance orientation are produced by the social dominance theory of gender and the complexity of social contextual forces (Schmitt & Wirth, 2009).

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Current Research

The present research paper aimed to develop a social dominance orientation scale towards caste/category and Hindi translation of social dominance scale, which was developed by Pratto et al (2014). Researches on social dominance orientation scale reveal the factor structures. Sidanius and Pratto (1999) developed 14 item social dominance orientation scales and found to be one-dimensional. However, Jost and Thomsen (2000) suggest pro trait and con trait section of 16 item social dominance orientation scale which was developed by Pratto et al (1994). Out of these pro and cons trait, one was to support group-based dominance hierarchies (SDO-D) and other was to suggest group-based equality. The 16-item social dominance orientation scale (Pratto et al. 1994), has been translated and used in many cultures (e.g., Aiello, Chirumbolo, Leone, & Pratto, 2005; Lee et al., 2011; Meyer, 2012) as a measure of propensity for prejudice. Social dominance orientation correlates positively with endorsement of legitimize inequality ideologies, such as racism, sexism, and nationalism, using a variety of culturally appropriate measures, and negatively with endorsement of ideologies that advocate for greater inclusiveness and equality, and with support for policies that would promote these principles (Lee et al., 2011).

The present study was a part of post-doctoral research in which authors were searching appropriate measure for social dominance orientation in context of three social categories (general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category) in Indian context and in Hindi language. Modified Delphi Technique was used to determine the social dominance orientation measures. Two measures were suggested by expert committee in which, one scale should be triggered to caste category system and other should be original scale of social dominance orientation in Hindi language. many situations occurred before authors in testing social dominance orientation, because egalitarianism has become more normative in many nations (Inglehart, Norris, & Welzel, 2002). Further, the usefulness of assessment of dominance motives (Sears, Haley, & Henry, 2008) such as scores on 1–5 and 1–7, social dominance scales were typically skewed positively, with very few people at the midpoint or higher. However, the scale still correlates robustly with a variety of criterion variables, indicating that variability of scores on the scale is socially and psychologically meaningful (e.g., Lee et al., 2011). Next, using student samples in prejudice research has been criticized for inflating results (Henry, 2008; but see Cohrs & Stetzl). Sometimes, only a subset of the items works to predict criterion variables (e.g., Freeman, Aquino, & Mc Ferran, 2009). Fewer items are more efficient for participants and researchers, and brief personality measures have become common (e.g., Rammstedt & John, 2007). Alternative translations of social dominance orientation scale items into the same language (e.g., Cohrs, Moschner, Maes, & Kielmann, 2005; Six, Wolfradt, & Zick, 2001), and use of different subsets of the 16 items, are abounding. To standardize the scale across countries, it is important to ensure that local connotations of particular words and phrases have comparable meaning, especially for languages spoken in many countries. The pro-trait and con trait aspects of the scale are confounded with item wording and may produce two factors (Six et al., 2001). Although social dominance theory was intended to pertain to all complex societies, the psychological focus of social dominance orientation, group dominance versus equality, may be a product of western political psychological history. If social dominance orientation primarily makes sense to people influenced by this cultural milieu, its robustness would be curtailed and new theorizing would be required (Pratto F, Çidam A, Stewart AL, et al 2013).

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The main objective of the study was to develop a social dominance orientation scale for Hindi language people and translation of four items social dominance orientation scale of Pratto et al (1994).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Measures

Development of SDO towards caste/category scale: Collection of literature on social dominance orientation carried out and reviewed. Different measures with varied items of social dominance scale (14 items, 16 items, 4 item and so on) found. Items of social dominance orientation reflected to group of people. Initially, we selected 16 item social dominance orientation scale. Scale translated in Hindi language and administered on a sample of 126 students. Findings of the pilot study presented on the departmental research committee. Difference among groups were not found on this scale. Although, past studies on explicit self-esteem and implicit self-esteem support the hierarchy about self-esteem, especially implicit self-esteem with name and surname tasks (Tiwari, Patel and Kumar 2017). In a study of group favouritism and perceived discrimination, Tiwari, Kumar and Pandey (2014) found that scheduled caste/scheduled tribe categories members manifested out-group favouritism and perceive discrimination more in comparison to general category and other backward category. Expert committee suggested that items of social dominance orientation scale should be translated in Hindi language in context of caste category. Even they suggested that statements related to social groups were unable to trigger the matter of caste/category dominance, whereas, Indian caste category content is prominent in social groups. Therefore, items of social dominance orientation scale translated in Hindi language and modified in terms of caste/category. To check Item translation and its appropriateness English language experts consulted. Eight items selected for Hindi language scale, four items for dominance enhancement and remaining four for dominance attenuation. Participants were asked to rate their agreement or disagreement with each statement using a scale ranged from (1) strongly disagree to (7) strongly agree. Items made balanced in terms of dominance enhancement and dominance attenuation statements to minimize the effect of response set. A total score can be derived by summing the scores on the individual items of each dimensions. A high score on the dominance enhancement may represent an indication of dominance among groups and high score on dominance attenuation reflects the follower of social equality. The minimum possible score on each scale dimension will be four and the maximum score will be 28. Internal consistency and construct validity of the scale were evaluated. To assess convergent and divergent validity, participants completed the trait rating about social categories scale and discrimination behaviour treatment towards social categories.

Hindi Translation of Four Items Social Dominance Orientation Scale (Pratto et al 2013): For the Hindi translation of social dominance orientation scale, we contacted the author and permission was taken regarding the translation. After that four-item social dominance orientation scale translated in Hindi language according to the guideline of WHO back translation. Out of four items of the scale, two items promote greater degree of social in equality, and another two items promote greater social equality. These two dimensions of social dominance orientation scale reflect two varieties of legitimizing myths: hierarchy enhancing and hierarchy attenuating. All items were answered on seven-point scale ranging one (strongly agree/disapproval) and seven (strongly agree/approval).

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Behavioral Orientation in Inter Group Relations Scale (Tiwari and Kumar 2020): present researcher developed it. It contains four types of behavioral orientations trait rating, namely discrimination treatment, intergroup preference, aggression and violence. Items of each behavioral orientation were repeated three times, one for own self-category and rest two for other social categories for example, each subject of a given category gave his response for own social category and other two social category. Responses taken on four-point scale. Description of four behavioral orientations and its psychometric properties is mentioned below:

Trait rating about social categories scale: It contains nine items of different area about three social categories group level characteristics i.e. skills, occupation, family background, family modality, customs, rituals, contribution in society and life styles. Items reflect about cognitive structure of three social categories. Mean score of each social category for self-category and other categories gives the comparative score of inter-group perception. Scores reveal the in-group favoritism and out-group favoritism of the members of these social categories. Scale has good psychometric properties. Alpha (α) found to be .79 for general category, 0.83 for other backward category and 0.86 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category.

Discrimination behavior treatment towards social categories scale: It has seven items of discrimination behavior treatment. Items focused to intergroup discrimination treatment of social categories in context of Hindi language region. This scale was developed to assess the level of discrimination among three social categories viz. self-category and other categories. Participants responded their perceived discrimination against in-group and out-group membership. Chronbach's alpha (α) calculated to estimate reliability coefficient. Alpha (α) found to be 0.84 for general category, 0.74 for other backward category and 0.80 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category.

Intergroup Preference among Social Categories Scale: It contains five items and assess the group preferences among social categories. Participants were presented a situation in statement form and asked them for their responses on that situation in context of self-category and other two categories. Chronbach's alpha (α) was found to be 0.78 for general category, 0.69 for other backward category and 0.78 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category.

Aggression and Violence towards Social Categories Scale: This scale contains five items, which reflect aggression and violence situation in context of social categories. Items were focused to violation of boundary line of caste/category. Each participant asked to give their response towards that particular caste/category viz. violation of rule and regulation explicitly. Sensitive case regarding caste/ category conflicts such as insult of caste and its related matters were presented and asked their responses (what will you do?) in term of self-category and other social categories. In-group and out-group responses were taken on four-point scale ranging keep quite (1), discussed (2), hard talk (3) and fight (4). Coefficient of alpha (α) was found to be 0.70 for general, 0.68 for other backward category and 0.70 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category.

Participants and Procedure

Three hundred sixty participants recruited from different departments of university campus and its affiliated colleges. All the participants were students of three social categories

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identified by the certificate given by provincial/ Indian government as general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category. At the time of data collection, ethical approval obtained from the university research committees. Students selected for the study were pursuing their regular courses. After completion of all the official formalities, student contacted individually and briefed about the study. After given consent to participate in the study, their contact numbers and address noted. We took appropriate precautions to establish rapport in context of social category issues and reservation policy. In the data collection sessions focus were given on research topic to avoid irrelevant issues related to caste/category.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences for Windows 10. Factor analysis and other relevant analysis to check psychometric properties performed. Correlation and descriptive statistics were also calculated.

RESULTS

Factor Structure of Social Dominance Orientation towards Caste/Category Scale: Obtained score subjected to inter item correlation. Items of SDO Caste/Category reflecting dominance and dominance attenuation found correlated to each other significantly in their respective group. A factor analysis using principal component extraction method with varimax rotation on eight items computed. KMO Bartlett's test of sampling adequacy found to be appropriate (0.68). The Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant [$\chi^2 (28) = 309.77, p < .01$]. Rotation converged in three iterations. Rotated factor structure yielded two components above the Eigenvalue of One (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Scree plot of social dominance orientation of caste/category scale in Hindi

Table 1: Rotated component matrix of social dominance orientation towards caste/ category scale.

Item No.	Factor-1	Factor-2
Item-1	.073	.656
Item-2	.717	-.158
Item-3	-.244	.636
Item-4	.471	.197
Item-5	-.242	.670

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Item No.	Factor-1	Factor-2
Item-6	.699	-.111
Item-7	.190	.647
Item-8	.707	-.059

Four items (item no. 2, 4, 6, 8) loaded on factor one, whereas, another four items (item no. 1, 3, 5, 7) loaded on factor two. First factor explained 23.54% variance, whereas, 22.82% variance were explained by second factor. Total 45.82% variance explained by these two factors (Table-1). Items of factor one denotes dominance attenuation and items of second factor indicate dominance enhancement.

Factor Structure of Social Dominance Orientation Scale (Pratto et al 2013): Obtained data on Four item social dominance scale entered for factor analysis. Principal component extraction method with varimax rotation used. Sampling adequacy test of KMO Bartlett found appropriate (0.51). The Bartlett's test of sphericity was found significant [$\chi^2 (6) = 77.56, p < .01$]. Rotations converged in three iterations. Rotated factor structure found two components above the eigenvalue one (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Scree plot of 4 item social dominance orientation scale in Hindi

Two items (item no. 1 and 3) loaded on first factor, whereas, another two items (item no. 2, and 4) loaded on second factor (Table-2).

Table-2: Rotated component matrix of social dominance orientation scale in Hindi language.

Item No.	Factor-1	Factor-2
Item-1	.671	-.243
Item-2	-.438	.570
Item-3	.846	.164
Item-4	.103	.893

First factor explained 34.19 % variance whereas 30.21 % variance explained by second factor. Total 64.41% variance explained by these two factors. First factor represents the hierarchy attenuation and second factor indicates towards hierarchy enhancement.

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Internal Consistency

Chronbach's alpha (α) computed for both dimensions. Alpha (α) for dominance enhancement found to be 0.60 for general category, 0.57 for other backward category and 0.48 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category. Alpha (α) for dominance attenuation were 0.51 for general category, 0.65 for another backward category and 0.55 for scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category. Overall Chronbach's alpha (α) was 0.57 for dominance enhancement and 0.56 for dominance attenuation (Table-3).

Table 3: Coefficient of Chronbach's alpha for each three social categories of both dimensions of social dominance orientations towards caste category

Scale dimensions	Social category	Chronbach's alpha
Dominance Enhancement	General	.60
	OBC	.57
	SC/ST	.48
	Total	.57
Dominance Attenuation	General	.51
	OBC	.65
	SC/ST	.55
	Total	.56

Reliability coefficient of alpha calculated for both dimensions in term of administered sample. Chronbach's alpha (α) estimated for both dimensions. Overall Chronbach's alpha (α) was found to be 0.35 for hierarchy enhancement and 0.41 for hierarchy attenuation (Table-4).

Table 4: Coefficient of Chronbach's alpha for each social categories of both dimensions of social dominance orientation scale

Scale dimensions	Social category	Chronbach's alpha
Hierarchy Enhancement	General	.44
	OBC	.29
	SC/ST	.30
	Total	.35
Hierarchy Attenuation	General	.42
	OBC	.26
	SC/ST	.58
	Total	.41

Relationship Analysis for the Social Dominance Orientation Scale and Behavioural Orientation Scales: The relationship between the social dominance orientation scale and subscales of behavioural orientations examined. It is evident from the table 5 that dominance enhancement is positively correlated with trait rating about general category ($r=.21, p<.05$) trait rating about other backward category ($r =.214, p<.05$) and preference to general category ($r=.231, p<.05$).

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Table-5: Correlations among dimensions of social dominance orientations and behavioral orientations of general category

Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Dominance		Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Enhancement	Attenuation	Enhancement	Attenuation
Trait rating about general category	.219*	-.039	.248*	.078
Trait rating about obc category	.241*	-.098	.188*	.075
Trait rating about sc/st category	.094	-.183*	.388**	-.012
Perceived discrimination about general category	.046	-.071	.136	.026
Perceived discrimination about obc category	.045	-.034	.023	-.048
Perceived discrimination about sc/st category	.146	-.111	.240**	.006
Preference to general category	.231*	-.054	.275**	-.173
Preference to obc category	-.082	.032	.030	.025
Preference to sc/st category	-.018	.036	-.062	-.051
Aggression and violence to general category	.060	-.259*	.055	-.095
Aggression and violence to obc category	-.021	.031	.069	-.223*
Aggression and violence to sc/st category	.014	.040	.084	.045

Note: ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

Dominance attenuation is found to be negatively correlated with trait rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=-.183, p<.05$), aggression and violence to general category ($r=-.259, p<.05$).

Hierarchy enhancement was found positively correlated with trait rating about general category ($r=.248, p<.05$), trait rating about other backward category ($r=.188, p<.05$) and trait

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rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.388, p<.01$), perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.240, p<.01$) and general category preference ($r=.275, p<.01$). Hierarchy attenuation was found negatively correlated with aggression and violence to other backward category ($r=-.223, p<.05$).

Dominance enhancement was positively correlated with trait rating about other backward category ($r=.180, p<.05$), perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.218, p<.05$), aggression and violence to general category ($r=.292, p<.01$). Dominance attenuation is significantly correlated with perceived discrimination about other backward category ($r=.223, p<.05$) in response table of other backward category (Table6). Significant positive relationship was found among hierarchy enhancement and trait rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.203, p<.01$), preference to other backward category ($r=.271, p<.05$), aggression and violence to general category ($r=.367, p<.01$).

Table-6: Correlations among dimensions of social dominance orientations and behavioral orientations of other backward category

Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Dominance		Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Enhancement	Attenuation	Enhancement	Attenuation
Trait rating about general category	.154	-.012	.061	.038
Trait rating about obc category	.180*	.050	.106	-.158
Trait rating about sc/st category	.175	-.159	.203*	-.039
Perceived discrimination about general category	-.077	.047	.112	-.021
Perceived discrimination about obc category	.125	.223*	.038	-.044
Perceived discrimination about sc/st category	.218*	-.142	.308	-.077
Preference to general category	.075	-.078	.158	-.067
Preference to obc category	.024	.011	.271*	-.106
Preference to sc/st category	.152	.061	.142	-.129
Aggression and violence to general category	.292**	-.117	.367**	-.267

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Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Dominance		Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Enhancement	Attenuation	Enhancement	Attenuation
Aggression and violence to obc category	.078	-.091	.134	-.037
Aggression and violence to sc/st category	-.091	.028	.111	-.043

*Note: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$*

Hierarchy attenuation was not correlated with any types of behavioural orientations in other backward category participants.

Table-7: Correlation among dimensions of social dominance orientations and behavioral orientations of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category

Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Dominance		Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Enhancement	Attenuation	Enhancement	Attenuation
Trait rating about general category	.122	-.083	.218*	.080
Trait rating about obc category	.079	.136	-.207	.051
Trait rating about sc/st category	.015	-.154	-.001	.012
Perceived discrimination about general category	.086	.017	.047	.070
Perceived discrimination about obc category	.151	-.064	.159	-.058
Perceived discrimination about sc/st category	.193*	.086	-.063	-.106
Preference to general category	.136	-.268**	-.028	-.153
Preference to obc category	-.045	.016	-.008	.107
Preference to sc/st category	.168	-.047	.289**	.059
Aggression and violence to general category	-.110	-.043	.261**	-.284

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Behavioral orientations	Dimensions of SDO Dominance		Dimensions of SDO Hierarchy	
	Enhancement	Attenuation	Enhancement	Attenuation
Aggression and violence to obc category	.213	-.227*	.109	-.164
Aggression and violence to sc/st category	-.082	-.076	.005	-.070

Table 7 illustrates the results of correlation of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category participants, a positive relationship was seen between dominance enhancement and perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.193, p<.05$). Dominance attenuation was negatively correlated with preference to general category ($r=-.268, p<.01$), aggression and violence to other backward category ($r=-.227, p<.05$). Hierarchy enhancement was positively correlated with trait rating about general category ($r=.218, p<.05$), preference to scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category ($r=.289, p<.01$), aggression and violence to general category ($r=.261, p<.01$). Hierarchy attenuation was not correlated with any behavioural orientations.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to develop social dominance orientation towards caste category scale and Hindi translation of four item social dominance orientation scale for three social categories namely general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category. The results suggested that the both scales were reliable and valid measure to assess social dominance orientation in Hindi language. In a study Serçekuş, P., İsbir, G. G., & İnci, F. H. (2017), mentioned that factor analysis is a commonly used method for evaluating construct validity. Construct validity refers to a scale's ability to measure the target concept and/or conceptual structure (Gozum and Aksayan, 2003). We found that factor loadings of the items ranged from .47 to .71 for social dominance orientation towards caste category scale and .57 to .84 for four item social dominance orientation scale. These values demonstrate the construct validity of the scale (Burn and Grove, 2001; Laher, 2010; Stevens, 1996). These results were indicating strong validity of both scales items.

The internal consistency of the social dominance orientation towards caste category was satisfactory (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.51$ to $.60$) and (Cronbach $\alpha = .30$ to $.44$) for four item social dominance orientation scale in Hindi language. One explanation may be that the alpha coefficient decreases when the number of items in a scale decrease (field 2009). The lower values of alpha for both scale factors are indicating about the relationship with cultural background and institutional practices regarding caste category or group dominance. Past studies suggest that three social categories of Indian societies classified in groups as per reservation system of caste and class system. In new era of Indian society, it is assumed that, policy regarding empowerment for under-privileged people, or caste category is unreachable to remote areas. Present study was conducted on town area of a district where new organizations for caste category have been made a shape. Students of university and college were participated in various caste category welfare programs and make aware to another students. To determine the convergent validity of both scales, behavioural orientation scale was implemented. In general category members, findings of the correlation established the

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positive relationship with trait rating about general category, trait rating about other backward category and preference to general category, whereas, dominance attenuation has negative relationship with trait rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, aggression and violence to general category. Hierarchy enhancement established the positive relationship with trait rating about general category, trait rating about other backward category, trait rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category and perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, whereas, hierarchy attenuation was established negative relationship with aggression and violence to other backward category. In other backward category members, dominance enhancement established the positive relationship with trait rating about other backward category, perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, whereas, dominance attenuation established the positive relationship with perceived discrimination about other backward category. Hierarchy enhancement was found to be relationship with trait rating about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, preference to other backward category; aggression and violence to general category whereas, hierarchy attenuation could not establish any relationship with dimensions of behavioral orientation. In scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members, dominance enhancement established the positive relationship with perceived discrimination about scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, whereas, dominance attenuation established negative relationship with preference to general category, aggression and violence to other backward category. Hierarchy enhancement established the positive relationship with trait rating about general category, preference to scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category, aggression and violence to general category. Pratto et al (1994) defined social dominance orientation as individual preference for group hierarchy and inequality and have been under grid, an impressive array of intergroup phenomena that serve to enhance or attenuate group-based hierarchy. Hierarchy enhancement/ dominance enhancement promote the greater degree of social inequality, whereas, hierarchy attenuation/ dominance attenuation contributed to greater social equality. Dominance enhancement/hierarchy enhancement items suggest the approval of group that “use force” and “step on other groups”, support to aggressive and prejudicial behaviour in groups. Dominance attenuation/ hierarchy attenuation accounts for significant variation in conservatism, opposition to international diplomacy, anti-black attitude, just world beliefs and opposition to redistributive social policies (Cohrs, Moschner, Maes and Keilmann 2005; Kuglar, Cooper and Nosek 2010, Sears et al 2008). Arnold, K. H. et al (2012) describe in their article that two major distinct psychological orientation of social dominance orientation are: SDO-Dominance and SDO– Egalitarianism. Factor structure of SDO tools in context of Hindi language confirms these dimensions. Both scales have been found two dimensions which is named by Dominance Enhancement and Dominance Attenuation (SDO scale towards caste category), and Hierarchy Enhancement and Hierarchy Attenuation (4 items SDO scale). Sidanius and Pratto (1993) defined both term of social dominance orientation and said that SDO-D supports to group-based dominance hierarchies in which dominant groups actively oppress the subordinate groups and SDO-E is opposition to group-based equality. Both dimensions are differently corresponding with group relevant variable. SDO-E dimension is accountable for conservatism opposition to international diplomacy, anti-black attitude, just world beliefs and opposition to redistributive social policies (Cohns, Moschner, Maes, and Kielmann 2005, Krugler, Coopers and Nosek 2010; Yoshimura and Hardin 2009). Another side of SDO-D dimension predicted to discrimination against women and homosexuals (Eagly et al 2004).

CONCLUSION

Both Hindi language scales are valid instrument for measuring social dominance among three social categories namely general category, other backward category and scheduled caste scheduled tribe category. Study results confirms the reliability of scale dimensions i.e., dominance enhancement and dominance attenuation in social dominance orientation towards caste category scale, hierarchy enhancement and hierarchy attenuation in 4 item social dominance orientation scale. The test for reliability of the individual subscales yielded unsatisfactory results. It is probable that limited number of items of the scales and study sample of main city was responsible for low internal consistency results. We recommended that in future studies of Indian social groups should be conducted on remote areas. Because, belief system about caste category stereotypes is still found in remote areas which has proven by past studies.

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